

AUTOMATIC SANITARY NAPKIN VENDING MACHINE

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Abstract: The use of automatic sanitary napkin vending machine can help women in maintaining hygiene during menstrual period. The main objective of sanitary vending machine is to give hygiene sanitary napkins with reasonable cost and the machine can be easily installed anywhere utilizing less space. Vending of napkin is done when user drops the coin. The system works successfully when sensing of coin is done. By installing automatic sanitary napkin vending machine in rural areas, school, colleges, hospitals etc, we can provide an easy access to napkins so that during emergency situations women need not face any difficulty

Keywords: Sanitary Napkin, Vending Machine,

1.INTRODUCTION

We are living in 21st century and humans are making development to next level but one main problem arising with this development is health. Social status with health inequalities plays important role to serve the country. According to world health organization, worst health of people is due to lower social economics. Therefore, the solution to this problem is necessary. In all over the world out of total health issues, women contribute to most of the percent. Thus, female hygiene is more important and is needed to be taken care. Most of the health problems of women are caused due to menstrual cycle. Due to unavailability of facilities, almost 23% of girls drop out of the school during the time of menstruation. Women in India are still shy of buying napkin from medical shops and other stores. Thus, proper awareness and availability of napkin is very much important. A solution to this problem is installing automatic sanitary napkin vending machine in school, college and public places, working and educational institutions, which would help them to get the napkins as and when they require. On an average, each woman uses more than 10,000 sanitary napkins during menstrual cycle. Blood soiled sanitary napkins are favorable medium for disease causing bacteria such as Escherichia coli and viruses to grow rapidly. According to research, when blood on used sanitary pads is exposed to the air, approximately 100,000 bacteria will grow on it within four minutes. The red blood cells in the menstrual blood nourish the bacteria and emit a foul odour when they die. This cause a major pollution issue including lots of plastic waste. Adoption of sanitary napkins is less than 20% in India whereas adoption of cosmetics like lipstick are significantly higher than 65%. Lack of menstrual hygiene is always a challenge in India. According to UNESCO, 23 million girls drop out of school due to lack of menstrual hygiene and awareness. It is a general problem among women where there is lack of availability of napkins during emergency situations and most of them hesitate to take help in such situations. Educating and creating awareness to use sanitary napkins and further provide quick access to sanitary napkins using machine is of prime needs.

2.LITERATURE REVIEW

Lewis A Babiarz .et.al, the proposed design discusses with a liquid flow sensor based on the measurement of the pressure difference across a flow restriction integrated between 2 silicon pressure sensors [1]. Bardten schlager R: The proposed design discusses about automatic process control for vacuum dispensing equipment with control on pressure and temperature [2]. Klocke J: The article discusses about the challenges such as package sizes decrease, under fill materials advance and tolerances tighten in automating the underfill dispensing process for robust production. The best practices for automated under fill dispensing are discussed for various types of under fill packages [3]. Hong Gu, Shuang Qiao and Jiang Tian: GSM network based Wireless Vending machine was designed based on USSD platform. It also manages sale information, logistic information and consumer information online [4]. Liu Xiangquan: The proposed prototype discusses about designing and application for automated medicine depositing and dispensing system of pharmacy. Total design of medicine depositing, hardware of control system, application of multi-threading technology and analysis of control requirements, control methods for actuating equipment's were discussed [5]. Kim K.Park D.Bang H, Hong G and Jin S: The article discusses about smart coffee vending machine using sensor and actuator networks. A sensor and actuator network and install it inside a vending machine to monitor the indoor environment of the machine and it adjusts the coffee taste [6]. Penna M.Gowda D V, Jijesh JJ and Shivashankar: The article discusses about automatic medicine dispensing machine design for the benefit of people in remote tribal areas where Government/agencies struggle in distributing to the need on emergency. The prototype consists of a micro-controller and motor-based system to dispense the medicines when accessed by the user through an input event [7]. Zhang W and Zhang: The article discusses about automatic vending machine based on short message payment. It describes about the design of vending machine and the method to use short message payment [8]. Low C Y, Chong K H, Johnny K SP

and Tiong SK,: Liquid dispensing system for various liquids of different viscosity elaborated with real-time automatic control by using an analytical balance reading. The design results in higher accuracy and precision in shorter duration [9]

2.MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

As per study only 36% of girls use Sanitary Napkins all over India. It's observed that 20 percent of girls didn't use toilet in class during menstruation for fear of staining it, and over 2 out of 5girlshadnoideaabout menstruation after they started with their periods. Of those who had some idea, only 16percent received any information in class. There is a possible loss on economic and social front to India; as a result, many of the girls are not able to share their menstrual health issues and thus stepping into early marriages and early pregnancies. More girls in schools means universal primary education are not at all educating the girls about periods and what all things we need to take care while period's stage comes. Educated mother should contribute and educate her child of taking precautions using of sanitary napkins. Hence, educating and creating awareness to be used of sanitary napkins and furthermore provide quick access to sanitary napkins using machine is of prime need. Thus, in India some places, women use clothes rather than sanitary napkins. The employment of garments may cause health issues. When girls reach the menstruating age, families are making their child to drop of colleges and get married. 79 percent of women and girls are not alert to menstrual hygiene practice.

Table 1: Materials Used

SL.NO	PARTS	QTY	MATERIAL
1	METAL BOX	1	GS SHEET
2	COIN ACCEPTOR	1	-
3	VENDING MOTOR	2	-
4	MECHANICAL SPRING	2	STEEL
5	CONTROL BOARD	1	ELECTRONICS
6	LCD DISPLAY	1	ELECTRONICS

Figure.1 a. Methodology Flow chart, b. Block Diagram

METAL CASE: A metal box is used to accommodate all the components such as spring, vending motor, coin acceptor and to store the napkins.

COIN ACCEPTOR: Coin acceptor means the slot and accompanying device, approved by the division, that is the part of as slot machine into which a patron, in the normal course of operating the machine, inserts a coin or slot token for the purpose of activating play and which is designed to identify those coins or slot tokens so inserted.

VENDING MOTOR Vending motor is used to rotate the mechanical spring. A DC motor is any of a class of electrical machines that converts direct current electrical power into mechanical power. The most common types rely on the forces produced by magnetic fields. Nearly all types of DC motors have some internal mechanism, either electro magnetically or electronic; to periodically change the direction of current flow in part of the motor. In this system, the DC Motor of operational voltage and Most types produce rotary motion.

MECHANICAL SPRING A spring is an elastic object that stores mechanical energy. Springs are typically made of spring steel. There are many spring designs. In everyday use, the term often refers to coil springs.

Figure.2 a. Metal Box, b. Coin Acceptor c. Vending Motor

Figure.3 a. AC Supply, b. Control Board c. LCD Display

Figure 4a GS Metal sheet

Figure 4b Welded box

Figure 4c Sheet cutting

Figure 4d CAD Drawing

FABRICATION: Fabrication is done as per the design and modification done by taking a suitable material as per the requirement. The metal sheet is cut according to the required dimensions and welded together to make a box. The temperature for welding is kept low as per the requirements of the metal sheet. Slots are cut to fix the motors, coin acceptor and display. The edges of the box are ground to provide a smooth finishing. The box is painted with primer and metal paint on the outer. Aluminum paint is used in the interior of the box. Gs metal sheet is cut into six pieces according to the dimensions of length 100cm, breadth 45cm and width 23cm. The sheet is cut using 4mm thick blade and then welded together using electric arc welding in low temperature, since the thickness of metal

DESIGN:

A suitable and simple design for the vending machine is created. A casual drawing of design has been done. The design of the vending machine is a metal box which can be easy installed in needful places. Component for input which is the multiple coin acceptor is placed in front along with a LCD display for showing the necessary information. The selection switches are also provided for selecting the type of item required. Two vertical cutouts are provided on the door to show the availability of stock inside and an opening to collect the product. The vending motors are fixed at the top end of the box and springs are attached vertically to the vending motor. The box is of dimensions 100×45×23 cm. Slots for two items and coin collection are provided inside the box.

3.RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

WORKING

The user can drop a coin through the slot provided. After the insertion and sensing of the coin, execution of method starts. The machine helps to produce a sanitary pad on sensing 5 rupee. It can also sense a combination of 2 rupee and Rs.1 coin and also reject other denomination coins. A display is provided to show the basic information such as price, availability of stock and user-friendly information. The pads are stacked in the spring which is held vertical. After inserting Rs.5, the vending motor rotates clockwise to complete one full turn, and the napkin at the bottom of the stack falls at the dispensing point where the user can collect it. The vending machine can work in three different modes - single, double and auto. In single mode, only one spring is operated which can be used for one type of pad. In double mode, two springs can be used for two different sizes of sanitary pads at different price, if necessary, which can be selected using the selection switch. The display shows useful information of price and number of stock available in each spring. In auto mode, all the racks (40+40) act as a single product and the second spring starts rotating once the entire rack in the first spring is empty.

TOTAL COST OF THE PROJECT

SL.NO.	PARTICULARS	AMOUNT
1	METAL BOX	2300
2	COIN ACCEPTOR	1500
3	VENDING MOTOR	1200
4	MECHANICAL SPRING	800
5	SWITCHES	40
6	AC SUPPLY	300
7	CONTROL BOARD	2500
8	PAINT	600
9	LCD DISPLAY	250
	TOTAL	9490

4.CONCLUSION

The purpose of this work is to give an easy way of availability of napkin. Vending of napkin is done when user drops the coin. The system works successfully when sensing of coin is done. As per study in India only 12% of women use sanitary napkins and percentage is much lower in rural areas. This is caused due to lack of awareness among them. Women health

is very sensitive and is needed to be taken care immediately and during the period of menstruation proper facilities must be provided. Most of the women in India are still shy of buying napkins from shops or medical store. The solution to this problem is by installing automatic sanitary napkin vending machine in rural areas, school, colleges, hospitals, etc. Our aim is to provide an easy way of availability of napkin so that during emergency situations women's need not face any difficulties

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